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A remark on locally direct product subsets in a topological Cartesian space

Hiroki Yagisita (Kyoto Sangyo University)

Abstract:

Let X and Y be topological spaces. Let C be a path-connected closed set of $X \times Y$. Suppose that C is locally direct product, that is, for any $(a, b) \in X \times Y$, there exist an open set U of X , an open set V of Y , a subset I of U and a subset J of V such that $(a, b) \in U \times V$ and

$$C \cap (U \times V) = I \times J$$

hold. Then, in this memo, we show that C is globally so, that is, there exist a subset A of X and a subset B of Y such that

$$C = A \times B$$

holds. The proof is elementary. Here, we note that one might be able to think of a (perhaps, open) similar problem for a fiber product of locally trivial fiber spaces, not just for a direct product of topological spaces.

In Appendix, we mentioned a simple example of a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold that cannot be embedded in the direct product $(C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}))^n$ as a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold. In addition, we introduce the concept of topological 2-space, which is locally the direct product of topological spaces and an analog of homotopy category for topological 2-space. Finally, we raise a question on the existence of an \mathbb{R}^n -Morse function and the existence of an \mathbb{R}^n -immersion in a finite-dimensional \mathbb{R}^n -Euclidean space. Here, we note that the problem of defining the concept of an \mathbb{R}^n -handlebody may also be considered.

Keywords: Morse-Bott index, handle decomposition, universal covering space, foliated manifold, fiber bundle, fibration, holomorphic foliation, Stein manifold.

The related literature: “https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hiroki_Yagisita”

Proof :

[Step 1]

Let (x, y) is a continuous mapping from $[0, 1]$ to C . Then, in this step, we show that $(x(0), y(1)) \in C$ and $(x(1), y(0)) \in C$ hold.

Let

$$T := \{t \in [0, 1] \mid \forall (u, v) \in [0, t] \times [0, t] : (x(u), y(v)) \in C\}.$$

Then, $0 \in T$ holds. Because C is a closed set of $X \times Y$, T is a closed set of $[0, 1]$.

We show that for any $t_0 \in [0, 1) \cap T$, there exists $t_1 \in (t_0, 1]$ such that $[0, t_1] \subset T$ holds. Let

$$t_0 \in [0, 1) \cap T.$$

Let

$$D := \{(u, v) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \mid (x(u), y(v)) \in C\}.$$

Then, D is a closed set of $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$ and

$$\cup_{t \in [0, 1]} \{(t, t)\} \subset D$$

and

$$[0, t_0] \times [0, t_0] \subset D$$

hold. Because C is a locally direct product set of $X \times Y$, D is a locally direct product set of $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$. That is, for any $(a, b) \in [0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, there exist open sets U and V of $[0, 1]$, a subset I of U and a subset J of V such that $(a, b) \in U \times V$ and

$$D \cap (U \times V) = I \times J$$

hold. So, there exist open sets U_0 and V_0 of $[0, 1]$, a subset I_0 of U_0 and a subset J_0 of V_0 such that $(t_0, t_0) \in U_0 \times V_0$ and

$$D \cap (U_0 \times V_0) = I_0 \times J_0$$

hold. Then, from $t_0 \in [0, 1)$, there exists $t_2 \in (t_0, 1]$ such that

$$[t_0, t_2] \times [t_0, t_2] \subset U_0 \times V_0$$

holds. So, from $\cup_{t \in [t_0, t_2]} \{(t, t)\} \subset D$, $\cup_{t \in [t_0, t_2]} \{(t, t)\} \subset I_0 \times J_0$ holds. Hence, $[t_0, t_2] \times [t_0, t_2] \subset I_0 \times J_0$ holds. So,

$$[t_0, t_2] \times [t_0, t_2] \subset D$$

holds. Well, there exist $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n \in [0, t_0]$, open sets $U_1, V_1, U_2, V_2, \dots, U_n, V_n$ of $[0, 1]$ and sets $I_1, J_1, I_2, J_2, \dots, I_n, J_n$ such that

$$[0, t_0] \times \{t_0\} \subset \cup_{k=1,2,\dots,n} (U_k \times V_k)$$

holds and for any $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, $I_k \subset U_k$, $J_k \subset V_k$, $(a_k, t_0) \in U_k \times V_k$ and

$$D \cap (U_k \times V_k) = I_k \times J_k$$

hold. Then, from $0 \leq t_0 < t_2 \leq 1$, there exists $t_3 \in (t_0, t_2]$ such that

$$[t_0, t_3] \subset \cap_{k=1,2,\dots,n} V_k$$

holds. Let

$$S := \{u \in [0, t_0] \mid [u, t_0] \times [t_0, t_3] \subset D\}.$$

Then, from $0 \leq t_0 < t_3 \leq t_2 \leq 1$, $t_0 \in S$ holds. Because D is a closed set of $[0, 1] \times [0, 1]$, S is a closed set of $[0, t_0]$. Now, we show that for any $u_0 \in (0, t_0] \cap S$, there exists $u_1 \in [0, u_0]$ such that $[u_1, t_0] \subset S$ holds. Let $u_0 \in (0, t_0] \cap S$. Then, there exists $k_0 \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ such that $(u_0, t_0) \in U_{k_0} \times V_{k_0}$ holds. From $u_0 \in (0, t_0]$, there exists $u_1 \in [0, u_0]$ such that $[u_1, u_0] \subset U_{k_0}$ holds. Because $t_0 \in V_{k_0}$ and $[u_1, u_0] \times \{t_0\} \subset D$ hold, $[u_1, u_0] \times \{t_0\} \subset I_{k_0} \times J_{k_0}$ holds. So,

$$[u_1, u_0] \subset I_{k_0}$$

holds. On the other hand, from $u_0 \in S$ and $[t_0, t_3] \subset V_{k_0}$, $\{u_0\} \times [t_0, t_3] \subset D \cap (U_{k_0} \times V_{k_0}) = I_{k_0} \times J_{k_0}$ holds. So,

$$[t_0, t_3] \subset J_{k_0}$$

holds. Therefore, $[u_1, u_0] \times [t_0, t_3] \subset D$ holds. Hence, $u_1 \in S$ holds. So, for any $u_0 \in (0, t_0] \cap S$, there exists $u_1 \in [0, u_0]$ such that $[u_1, t_0] \subset S$ holds. Hence, S is a nonempty closed open set of $[0, t_0]$. Because $S = [0, t_0]$ holds,

$$[0, t_0] \times [t_0, t_3] \subset D$$

holds. Similarly, there exists $t_4 \in (t_0, t_2]$ such that

$$[t_0, t_4] \times [0, t_0] \subset D$$

holds. Therefore, as we set $t_1 := \min\{t_3, t_4\}$, $t_1 \in (t_0, 1]$ and $[0, t_1] \times [0, t_1] \subset D$ hold. So, for any $t_0 \in [0, 1) \cap T$, there exists $t_1 \in (t_0, 1]$ such that $[0, t_1] \subset T$ holds.

Therefore, T is a nonempty closed open set of $[0, 1]$. Because $T = [0, 1]$ holds, $(x(0), y(1)) \in C$ and $(x(1), y(0)) \in C$ hold. —

[Step 2]

Let

$$A := \{x \in X \mid \exists y \in Y : (x, y) \in C\}$$

and

$$B := \{y \in Y \mid \exists x \in X : (x, y) \in C\}.$$

Then, $C \subset A \times B$ holds. Let $(x_0, y_1) \in A \times B$. Then, we show that $(x_0, y_1) \in C$ holds. There exist $y_0 \in Y$ and $x_1 \in X$ such that $(x_0, y_0) \in C$ and $(x_1, y_1) \in C$ hold. Because C is path-connected, in virtue of Step 1, $(x_0, y_1) \in C$ holds. ■

Comment : Does there exist a \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N such that for any \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1 and M_2 , N can not be embedded in $M_1 \times M_2$ as a \mathbb{C}^2 -submanifold ? Kasuya proposed a candidate for such a compact \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N . Our result may be useful to prove that it is such. For the definition of a \mathbb{C}^n -manifold, see [1] or [2].

In [1], we proposed a candidate of a noncompact \mathbb{C}^2 -manifold N such that (1) for any \mathbb{C} -manifolds M_1 and M_2 , N can not be embedded in $M_1 \times M_2$ as a \mathbb{C}^2 -submanifold but (2) there exists $k \in \mathbb{N}$ such that N can be embedded in the k -dimensional Euclidean \mathbb{R}^2 -space $(\mathbb{R}^k)^2$ as an \mathbb{R}^2 -submanifold. —

Remark : For deformation of \mathbb{R}^n -structures and \mathbb{C}^n -structures, see Kodaira and Spencer, *Ann. of Math.*, 74 (1961), 52-100. —

Problem : A \mathbb{C} -holomorphically convex domain of \mathbb{C}^n is an n -dimensional Stein manifold. So, it is a closed \mathbb{C} -submanifold of \mathbb{C}^{2n+1} . Let C be a \mathbb{C}^2 -holomorphically convex domain. Then, is C the direct product of some Stein manifolds ? For the definition of \mathbb{C}^n -holomorphic convexity, see [2]. —

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Appendix 0

In [3], we gave a simple example of a connected metrizable 1-dimensional $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -manifold that cannot be embedded in the direct product space $(C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R}))^n$ as a $C([0, 1]; \mathbb{R})$ -submanifold.

Appendix 1

Definition 1 (2-space) :

$W := (W, S)$ is said to be a 2-space and S is said to be the system of local Cartesian neighborhoods of W , if it satisfies the followings.

(1) W is a topological space. S is a set.

(2) Let $\varphi \in S$. Then, φ is a homeomorphism from an open set W_φ of W to the direct product of topological spaces U_φ and V_φ .

(3) Let $\varphi_1, \varphi_2 \in S$ and $c \in W_{\varphi_1} \cap W_{\varphi_2}$. Then, there exist an open set M_1 of U_{φ_1} , an open set N_1 of V_{φ_1} , a map f from M_1 to U_{φ_2} and a map g from N_1 to V_{φ_2} such that $c \in \varphi_1^{-1}(M_1 \times N_1) \subset W_{\varphi_2}$ holds and for any $w \in \varphi_1^{-1}(M_1 \times N_1)$,

$$\varphi_2(w) = (f(\pi_U(\varphi_1(w))), g(\pi_V(\varphi_1(w))))$$

holds. Here, π_U is the projection from $U_{\varphi_1} \times V_{\varphi_1}$ to U_{φ_1} and π_V is the projection from $U_{\varphi_1} \times V_{\varphi_1}$ to V_{φ_1} .

(4) $W = \cup_{\varphi \in S} W_\varphi$ holds.

Example 2 (locally direct product subset) :

Let X and Y be topological spaces. Then, a locally direct product subset of $X \times Y$ is a 2-space.

Example 3 (2-product) :

Let (W_1, S_1) and (W_2, S_2) be 2-spaces. Then, for any $(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) \in S_1 \times S_2$, the map

$$(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) : W_{1, \varphi_1} \times W_{2, \varphi_2} \longrightarrow (U_{1, \varphi_1} \times U_{2, \varphi_2}) \times (V_{1, \varphi_1} \times V_{2, \varphi_2})$$

is a homeomorphism. So, the 2-product

$$W_1 \times_2 W_2 := (W_1 \times W_2, S_1 \times S_2)$$

is a 2-space. —

Definition 4 (2-map) :

Let h be a continuous map from a 2-space (W_1, S_1) to a 2-space (W_2, S_2) . Then, h is said to be a 2-map, if it satisfies the following.

Let $c \in W_1$, $\varphi_1 \in S_1$, $c \in W_{1,\varphi_1}$, $\varphi_2 \in S_2$ and $h(c) \in W_{2,\varphi_2}$. Then, there exist an open set M_1 of U_{1,φ_1} , an open set N_1 of V_{1,φ_1} , a map f from M_1 to U_{2,φ_2} and a map g from N_1 to V_{2,φ_2} such that $c \in \varphi_1^{-1}(M_1 \times N_1) \subset h^{-1}(W_{2,\varphi_2})$ holds and for any $w \in \varphi_1^{-1}(M_1 \times N_1)$,

$$\varphi_2(h(w)) = (f(\pi_U(\varphi_1(w))), g(\pi_V(\varphi_1(w))))$$

holds. Here, π_U is the projection from $U_{1,\varphi_1} \times V_{1,\varphi_1}$ to U_{1,φ_1} and π_V is the projection from $U_{1,\varphi_1} \times V_{1,\varphi_1}$ to V_{1,φ_1} .

Definition 5 (2-homotopy) :

Let h_0 and h_1 be 2-maps from a 2-space W_1 to a 2-space W_2 . Then, h_0 and h_1 said to be 2-homotopic, if there exists a continuous map H from $[0, 1] \times W_1$ to W_2 such that for any $t \in [0, 1]$, the map $w_1 \in W_1 \mapsto H(t, w_1) \in W_2$ is a 2-map and for any $w_1 \in W_1$, $H(0, w_1) = h_0(w_1)$ and $H(1, w_1) = h_1(w_1)$ hold.

Example 6 :

2-spaces $\{0\} \times (\mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z})$ and $(\mathbb{R}/\mathbb{Z}) \times \{0\}$ are homeomorphic. However, they are not 2-homotopy equivalent. —

Problem :

(1) For a compact Hausdorff space T , define T -space, T -product, T -map and T -homotopy.

(2) Do there exist a contractible compact Hausdorff space T and T -spaces such that the T -spaces are homeomorphic but not T -homotopy equivalent? —

Appendix 2

Let M be a paracompact connected \mathbb{R}^n -manifold. Let (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_n) be an \mathbb{R}^n -map from M to \mathbb{R}^n . Suppose that for any local Cartesian neighborhood $U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_n$, $(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) \in U_1 \times U_2 \times \dots \times U_n$ and $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$, the map

$$x_k \in U_k \mapsto f_k(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{k-1}, x_k, a_{k+1}, a_{k+2}, \dots, a_n) \in \mathbb{R}$$

is a Morse function on U_k . Then, does there exist $m \in \mathbb{N}$ such that M can be \mathbb{R}^n -immersed in the m -dimensional \mathbb{R}^n -affine space $(\mathbb{R}^m)^n$?

Related problem (Probably easy) : Let M be a compact foliation. Then, does there exist a Bott-Morse function f such that a critical manifold of f is a leaf of M and a leaf of M is contained in a level set of f ? —

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